

CASE STUDY OF URBAN PARKS : CENTRAL PARK OF NEW YORK AND SANJAY GANDHI NATIONAL PARK OF MUMBAI

Sabiha More

Associate Professor

Smt Surajba College Of Education, Juhu, Mumbai: 400049

aaisabiha@gmail.com

Abstract:

Environment is everything that is around. It can be living or non-living things. It includes physical, chemicals and other natural forces. Living things live in their environment. They constantly interact with it and change in response to conditions in their environment. We have seen green patches turning into a dessert, rivers submerge the areas, increased alkaline in the water levels and make loose the species like a pack of cards. If experts are to be believed, then we are losing between 10,000 and 100,000 species each year or are getting extinct each year. So we need to do thinking how and why should environment be saved. In cities we need environment more vehemently than any other part of the inhabitation. This paper examines the need for parks in a metro city. It compares two parks of two famous cities of the world.

The cities of the 20th Century are conurbation of region comprising a number of cities, large towns, and other urban areas that, through population growth and physical expansion, have merged to form one continuous urban or industrially developed area. In most cases, a conurbation is a polycentric urbanised area, in which transportation has developed to link areas to create a single urban labour market or travel to work area. Therefore with such heavy population its essential for people to have a place to rejuvenate for leading a healthy life. We need to have a place which would absorb the unhealthy elements like suspended carbon particle, carbon mono oxide and smog.

Any metro in the world needs to give breathing space to its inhabitant through medium

of parks in the middle or around the city. There are some famous parks at the major cities located in the world.

Rank	Name	Location	Size in acres	Description
1	Chugach State Park	Anchorage, United States	495,199.20	The region contains extensive ocean shoreline, abundant lakes, massive glaciers and ice fields.
2	Table Mountain National Park	Cape Town, South Africa	54,610.30	It is one of the richest floral regions in the world. Over 70% of the flowers are endemic to the Table Mountain. was chosen as one of the new seven world wonders.
3	Pedra Branca State Park	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	30,626.20	The park is part of the Carioca Mosaic and has been recognized by UNESCO as an Atlantic Forest Biosphere Reserve.
4	McDowell Sonoran Preserve	Scottsdale, United States	30,394.00	The Preserve is unique geologically and home to stunning geography, lush cacti forests and diverse besert wildlife.
5	Losiny Ostrov National Park	Moscow, Russia	28,664.20	The park occupies the joint of the Meshchera Lowlands and Klin-Dmitrov chine, which is the watershed of the Moskva River and Klyazma River

6	Sanjay Gandhi National Park	Mumbai, India	25,659.40	The area has a history dating back to the 4th century BCE. In ancient India Sopara and Kalyan were two ports in the vicinity that traded with ancient civilisations such as Greece and Mesopotamia
7	Franklin Mountains State Park	El Paso, United States	24,246.00	Pictograms and mortar pits confirm Native American presence in the mountains dating back more than 12,000 years who have used the natural resources when crossing the gap between the Franklin Mountains and the Juarez Mountains
8	Bayou Sauvage National Wildlife Refuge	New Orleans, United States	22,758.40	It offers wide ranges of natural habitat where one can mingle with our animals and have three monkey islands and alligator ponds.
9	Bukhansan National Park	Seoul, South Korea	19,748.70	The park contains forested areas, temples and granite peaks.

10	Margalla Hills National Park	Islamabad, Pakistan	17,386.00	The park is rich in biodiversity, especially rich in Sino-Himalayan fauna, most notably gray goral, barking deer and the Leopard.
No Rank	Central Park	Manhattan, New York City	778	Central Park is home to everything from horse carriages to street vendors, including an ice rink during winter and Strawberry Fields, a tribute to John Lennon.

The Objective of the study :

1. To compare the structure of the two parks i.e Central Park NewYork and Sanjay Gandhi National Park, Mumbai
2. The success story behind the two parks
3. To understand the secrets that makes an urban park either to thrive or to die

Limitation of the study:

- 1.This paper studies only two urban parks among 189 urban parks listed in the Universal Heritage site
2. This is a Library Research, only for Sanjay Gandhi National Park the writer has made a visit in the recent Past

Operational definition of the terms included in the study:

Case Study: instance of something used or analysed in order to illustrate a thesis or principle.

Urban Cities: Urban areas are created through urbanization and are categorized by urban morphology as cities, towns, conurbations or suburbs.

Park: a large area of land with grass and trees, usually surrounded by fences or walls, and specially arranged so that people can walk in it for pleasure or children can play in it.

The study done on the comparison between two parks and measure the success and failure of functioning of the parks:

THE CENTRAL PARK NEW YORK

THE SANJAY GANDHI NATIONAL PARK, MUMBAI

- If you look at the map itself, we can deduce that no body has bothered to cart a map for SGNP for years together. We don't have a map which shows how much of Park

is lost and how much of encroachment has increased, so total negligence of the park. A total of 28,951 illegal structures are built inside as well as around the periphery of SGNP, with over 25,000 structures inside the park (accounting for 10% of encroachments in Borivli), according to data from the forest department's headquarters in Nagpur, which asked SGNP to prepare an action plan to address the issue. The SGNP confirmed that these were current figures, with some of the major encroachments across parts of Malad (East), Dahisar (East), Manpada, Nahur, Appapada, Kandivli (East), Kokanipada, Kranti Nagar, Damu Nagar, Bhim Nagar, parts of Yeoor and Ghodbunder Road.

- If you look at the CP, New York you can see that the park was constructed in 1858 when we were launching our first struggle of independence. Since then till now it has not lost an inch of land.

COMPARISION

PARAMETERS	SGNP, MUMBAI	CENTRAL PARK, NEW YORK
MANAGEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central Park Conservancy, a private, not-for-profit organization
RECREATIONAL FACILITIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Nature In Shilonda Trail • Go For A Highest Point Trek • Go On A Lion And Tiger Safari • Cycle Around • The Van Rani Toy Train Ride 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carriage Parade • Protected bike lanes • New York Road Runners • 26 baseball fields • 2 ice skating rinks • Victorian Gardens seasonal amusement park

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Boating Ride 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An outdoor swimming pool • Central Park's glaciated rock outcroppings • New York Classical Theatre • The Public Theatre • The Central Zoo
<p>FLORA AND FAUNA</p>	<p>1,000 plant species, 251 species of migratory, land and water birds, 50,000 species of insects and 40 species of mammals. In addition, the park also provides shelter to 38 species of reptiles, 9 species of amphibians, 150 species of butterflies and a large variety of fish. All this is naturally provided by Mother Nature, no had to plant it artificially.</p>	<p>2011, Central Park had more than 20,000 trees, representing a decrease from the 26,000 trees that were located in the park in 1993. The majority of the trees are native to New York City. With few exceptions, the trees in Central Park were mostly planted or placed manually. Over four million trees, shrubs, and plants representing approximately 1,500 species were planted or imported to the park. There is a total of 303 bird species that have been seen in the park, 10 species of mammals and also 223 invertebrate species in Central Park.</p>

SPECIALITY	The karvi (or karvy) a shrub, as it is locally called in the Marathi language, only blooms once in eight years in a mass flowering covering the forest floor in a lavender blush.	Nannarrup hoffmani , a centipede species discovered in Central Park in 2002; it is one of the smallest centipedes in the world at about 0.4 inches
ARTS AND MONUMENTS	Kanheri Caves Mahakaali Caves	Since 1863, twenty-nine sculptures of Artists Poets, war Memorials, Poets, Historical Figures, Fictional Characters etc. Besides skating rinks, Amphitheatres, Opera stages etc.
VISITORS ANNUALLY	Around 2 million visitors visit this park annually.	Around 37.5 million visitors visit this park each year. Central Park's peak seasons are noted as January - March, and June - August.
REVENUE GENERATED	In 2016, the park drew over 13.5 lakh visitors and generated Rs. 9.63 crore in revenue	A 2009 study found that the city received annual tax revenue of over \$656 million

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY:

1. SGNP is a gift of mother nature which is neglected both by the people and the government both. Nobody seems to take care of the bounty given by nature probably because no efforts were made to create the park.

Compared to this CA park was man made, people took effort to make it. Central Park was difficult to construct because of the generally rocky and swampy landscape. Around 5 million cubic feet (140,000 m³) of soil and rocks had to be transported out of the park, and more gunpowder was used to clear the area than was used at the Battle of Gettysburg during the American Civil War.[More than 18,500 cubic yards (14,100 m³) of topsoil were transported from Long Island and New Jersey, because the original soil was neither fertile nor sufficiently substantial to sustain the flora specified in the Greensward Plan.

2. The SGNP Park has made no efforts to construct any recreational activities to attract people. Mumbai has a population of about 23 million, and it is cramped for place. There is no place for recreation, no time to unwinding, no stress living activity, how can the mental and physical health be good without these kinds of activity?

Compared to this the population of New York in 2019 is 20.106 Million. They have a plethora of activity to do in the middle of the city on a regular basis. They have variety, options, choices and activities to choose from. Naturally on the health index they are better than us in all parameters.

3. Protection of environment leads to protection of flora and fauna automatically. Their protection leads to a healthy environment and enhances quality of life. For these densely populated areas, it should have such BREATHING SPACES which have a healthy environment. SGNP has been shrinking by each passing day. Encroachment is done daily with the help of unscrupulous politician and builder lobby. Flora and fauna are vanishing rapidly.

Compare to this in CP if the flora is lost, if the species is dwindling special efforts are made to reintroduce it in the park. The caretakers and the administration are aware and alert about it. They take action on a SOS basis.

4. The Administration of SGNP is done by apex body Government of India, they can do anything single headedly without the bureaucracy creating any obstacle for it. The main problem is the lack of dedication, integrity, diligence and honesty. Compared to this CP is run by a non-profit organization where people are doing most of the duty as honorary and without getting paid, yet they make sure that the park is alive, flourishing and

thriving, in its true sense.

5. In the maintenance and administration of SNGP there is no involvement of general public is a must. Unless you make people accountable for their deeds in public life anything which is community based can't survive. SGNP , when people visit they think everything is a responsibility of the government.

Compared to this all activities done in CP is by the people and for the people which makes them more responsible and accountable for their behaviour towards environment and society in general.

6. Education is the only way to make people respect, conserve, nurture and care for environment. This should be done right from the first day of education journey of a child.

7. Only school is not responsible for conserving and sustainability of environment. Society, family, community and religion are equally responsible for making people environmentally educated, aware and informed about it.

“Never doubt that a small group of thoughtful, committed citizens can change the world; indeed, it is the only thing that ever has.”

—Margaret Mead

Reference:

Rosenzweig, R & Blackmar, E (1998). The Park and the People: A History of Central Park
1st Edition: Cornell University Press;

Rupesinghe, K. (1995) Multi-Track Diplomacy and the Sustainable Route to Conflict
Resolution, Cultural Survival Quarterly. (Fall 1995), pp. 13-18

Patkar, M., & Singh, S. (2007). Urban Renewal: At Whose Cost? Economic and Political
Weekly.

Zerah, M.H. (1997) Conflict between green space preservation and housing needs: The
case of Sanjay Gandhi National Park in Mumbai, Cities.

"Geological History of NYC Parks". New York City Department of Parks and Recreation.
Retrieved April 15, 2019.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Central_Park

<https://freetoursbyfoot.com/things-to-do-in-central-park/>